

Fresh larvae from the greenhouse colony (10 second-instar larvae/ mylar tube cage pushed into the mud around a hill of rice, 1 cage/replication) were used in 3 experiments established after the field plots were sprayed:

1. Rice hills and surrounding water directly caged in the field plots (sprayed plants and paddy water),
2. Rice hills removed from the sprayed field plots, placed in pots in the greenhouse, and immersed in fresh water (sprayed plants only), and
3. In the greenhouse, unsprayed potted rice hills immersed in plastic basins of paddy water which had been set in the field before insecticide application (sprayed paddy water only).

The effect of the insecticides in the 3 experiments was measured as larval mortality 48 hours after infestation.

The caseworm was readily controlled by all insecticides tested (Table 1). MTMC was significantly less effective, however, than the 10 other insecticides at 0.75 kg a.i./ha. Lower dosages should be tested in future trials.

Acid fuchsin technique to stain stylet sheaths of the rice bug *Leptocorisa* spp. feeding on rice grains

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The rice bug *Leptocorisa* spp. as a seed pest has not been evaluated adequately because of a lack of a definitive technique to associate injured rice grains or yield loss with feeding. The rice bug injures grains by feeding 1) on developing (milky stage) grains to cause unfilled grains, 2) during the dough stage to cause "pecky rice" (discoloration of mature grains), and 3) during the dough stage to cause weak point in the kernels. The first injury causes yield loss, the second and third impair grain quality.

Establishing an economic threshold depends on which kind of injury is important to farmers. A subsistence farmer is concerned primarily with rice bug damage that results in loss of

Table 2. Effects on caseworm larval mortality of foliar insecticides applied to rice plants, paddy water, or both. IRRI, 1980.

Insecticide ^a	Larval mortality ^b (%) 48 h after spraying of		
	Plants and paddy water ^c	Plants only ^c	Paddy water only ^d
MIPC 50 WP	100 a	100 a	100 a
Diazinon 20 EC	100 a	97 ab	100 a
Azinphos-ethyl 40 EC	100 a	90 ab	100 a
Chlorpyrifos 40 EC	100 a	97 ab	95 ab
BPMC 50WP	100 a	92 ab	95 ab
Malathion 57 EC	100 a	92 ab	85 ab
Carbaryl 85 WP	100 a	95 ab	75 bc
Endosulfan 35 EC	100 a	68 c	85 ab
Phosphamidon 50 IC	95 a	82 bc	80 bc
MTMC 50 WP	85 a	63 c	55 c
Mean	98	88	88

^a0.75 kg a.i./ha. WP = wettable powder, EC = emulsifiable concentrate. Applied 15 days after transplanting. ^bCorrected using Abbott's formula. 10 second-instar larvae per replication (one cage). In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. ^cAv, 4 replications. ^dAv, replications.

The supplementary studies on larval mortality support the conclusion that rice caseworm larvae are highly sensitive to insecticides (Table 2). When larvae were exposed to both sprayed plants and paddy water in the field mortality was high (85-100%) after 48 h. Mortalities were significantly lower with some

insecticides (MTMC, endosulfan, phosphamidon) when only the plants were sprayed or only the water was sprayed (MTMC, carbaryl, phosphamidon). Mortality means over all insecticides indicated equal effect from spraying either plants or paddy water. ■

weight (unfilled grains). Grain quality is important because prices for pecky and broken rice are lower. Therefore, subsistence farmers are concerned about control from postflowering to the dough stage. Market-oriented farmers should continue to monitor their fields until the hard-dough stage.

Because all three kinds of grain injury can be caused by factors other than rice bugs, techniques that link a given type of damage directly to rice bug feeding should be developed. Subsequently rice bug numbers in the field can be used in the establishment of economic thresholds. The insecticide check method for measuring yield differences between treated and untreated plots is not definitive because stem borers or leaf folders cannot be ruled out as factors causing yield loss during the grain filling period.

Two techniques commonly used to indicate rice bug injury to grains are: 1) visual inspection of grains for evidence of dark feeding marks on hulls, and kernels, or 2) boiling the grains in a 2%

solution of KOH for 5 minutes to clean hulls and kernels. One technique's disadvantage is that fungal organisms can also cause discolored hulls and kernels. KOH cleans surface blemishes caused by fungal organisms; however, there are fungi that can penetrate the kernels.

A stylet sheath staining technique developed by C. C. Bowling, Texas A and M University, working on the rice stink bug *Oebalus pugnax* has been used at IRRI for *Leptocorisa*. When a rice bug feeds on a rice grain, it secretes a proteinaceous stylet sheath. Stylet sheath can be stained with acid fuchsin dye. If an unfilled or discolored grain resulted from rice bug feeding, then a stylet sheath should be evident on the rice hull.

To stain the stylet sheaths, rice panicles are placed in a pan and submerged in a staining solution of 1 part each of phenol, lactic acid, and distilled water, and two parts glycerine, plus enough acid fuchsin to color the solution dark red.

After the rice panicles have been immersed in the stain solution (no heating is required) for 30 minutes, they are rinsed in tap water and air-dried. The panicles can be observed immediately, or stored for counting later. The stain solution can be reused.

Leptocorisa produces stylet sheaths that can be seen with the naked eye; however, magnification is advised. Whereas *O. pugnax* penetrates the rice hull with its mouthparts, *Leptocorisa* spp. prefers to feed at the juncture of the palea and lemma (see photo).

To assess rice bug injury, filled and unfilled grains from a random sample of stained rice panicles are removed and counted. The unfilled grains with stylet

Leptocorisa stylet sheaths (arrows) stained with acid fuchsin dye magnified 40 (a), 90 (b), and 120 (c) times. Note that feeding occurs at the juncture of the lemma and the palea. IRRI, 1980.

sheath are assumed to be caused by the rice bug. The filled grains with stylet sheaths are boiled in KOH to determine the number of pecky rice grains in the sample caused by rice bug feeding.

The acid fuchsin staining technique

has a practical value in not only determining economic thresholds, but also in evaluating insecticide performance and plant resistance studies. ■

***Leptocorisa acuta* vs *oratorius*: a clarification of rice bug species**

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Leptocorisa oratorius (Fabricius) and *L. acuta* (Thunberg) share a common distribution. In Philippine rice fields *L. oratorius* is more abundant than *L. acuta*. The Asian literature mentions *L. acuta* more often than *L. oratorius*. We

believe it is difficult for rice entomologists to identify these 2 species.

The distinctive characters that distinguish *L. oratorius* and *L. acuta* are in the table. Also see figure. ■

Characters that distinguish *L. oratorius* from *L. acuta*.

Character	<i>L. oratorius</i>	<i>L. acuta</i>
1. Body length (mm) male	19.0	13.0
female	18.5	16.3
2. Vento-lateral spots (abdomen)	Present, usually brown	Absent
3. Pair of dorso-lateral spots on collar	Absent	Present
4. Spot behind compound eye	Present, usually dark brown	Absent
5. Length of pointed paraclypeae (mm)	Long (0.92- 0.96)	Short (0.61 -0.73)
6. Posterior angle of pronotal disc	Bears no black spot	Bears a black spot
7. Color of pronotal disc	Uniformly pale yellowbrown without white margins	Multicolored, with white margins
8. Seventh abdominal tergum of male	Medially convex	Truncate (straight edged)
9. Seventh abdominal sternum of female	Curved to very slightly convex at center	Curved with a small triangular projection
10. Pygophore	Large, rectangular	Small, rounded
11. Genitalia		
<i>Male</i>		
a. Claspers	Curved and tapered along apices	Bifid at apices
b. Left lateral conjunctival appendage	Elongated and curved at base and apex	Reduced to spine-like
c. Frontal conjunctival appendage	Bears two sclerotized plates	Bears one, only the posterior
d. Ventral thecal appendage	Elongated, constricted at center, curved and pointed at base	Curved to shoe-shaped with broad apex
e. Membranous terminal appendage	Bulbous	Reduced to an apophysis
<i>Female</i>		
a. First gonocoxa	Elongated nearly three times as long as broad, with unequally curved sides	Small, with sinuate outer margins and rounded apices, with evenly curved sides
b. Spermatheca	Thick at midarea, with a median flange, round and coiled tube	Irregular with a median flange and a long coiled tube